

It is The impact of social networks on youth

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Abstract: This article shows the positive and negative aspect of social networks , which are developing day by day, in the worldview of young people.

Key words; Internet social networks, youth spirituality , mass communication , psychological effects on teenagers ,manipulation of tennage mind.

Introduction

difficult to imagine today's improving world without social networks .Because we learn about the news and changes that occur around the world almost through social networks .Even, the need for televisions in everyone's home has become much less due to the fast-spreading news on social media .Many benefits of social networks in termson information exchange ,communication between people at long and close dictances ,development of information technology ,science and innovation ,but also there are also disadvantages of electromagnetic radiation,the stress of losing information ,the virtual world ,which affects not only the spirituality of young ,such as addiction and mental illness.

Main body

A social networks is an online platform used for communication dating ,social relationships between people with similar interests or online connections ,as well as for entertainment music and movies and work purposes ,and it has a lot of shows that have a negative impact on the level of youth in various forms.Currently ,the most popular social networks around the world include sites,such as Telegram,Facebook,Twitter, Instagramm, You Tube ,Whats APP, TIK TOC . Snapchat, Reddit, Pinterest, LinkedIn [1].All kinds of fictitious, fantastic and militant games ,movies, video shows that are farbidden for minors to watch, and spreading secret information related to terrorism and exstremism through religions sites of various forms , which are dangerous to human life, have a negative impact on the spirituality of the young generation .

In December 2, 2021, an international conference was held in the Republic of Uzbekiston on the topic "The influence of the Internet and social networks on youth ".

It was attended by representatives of the ministries of innovative development ,improvement of information technology communications ,UNISEF, INXA ,University ,Institute for the Study of Youth Problems and Training of Prospective Personnel,Uzbek Journalists' Union, Information and Mass Communications Agency [2] For most of the youth representatives ,it is easier to communicate on the Internet that in real life ,and as a result ,it leaves a negative mark on a person's place in society and further limits it.In particular the role of social networks in communication tools such as mobile phones ,tablets, and computers is expanding in the upbringing of children.There is a big difference between the worldview of the children of the last century and the young generations of today .The thought of modern young is as fast as social network tools.Even the younger generation understand the programs that some older people do not understand .As a result ,negative situations are clearly visible in children's brain activity such as the use of educational resources, in particular, books, reading decreases,and social networks are filled with demonstrations.Since 2010,more than 8-800-2000-1228 million applications have been received on the All-Russia children's hotline.At the moment,222 services are connected to a single number in 83 regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan can get help[3].

The main risks for children and teenagers on the internet are;

- 1)Cyberbullying Internet bullying;
- 2)Using the Internet to manipulate the minds of children and teenagers(promoting extremist,anti-social behavior,committing suicide,engaging in dangerous games);
- 3)Cyber fraud;
- 4)Security of access to the network and theft of personal information by technical means;
- 5)Unlawful collection of personal information of minors and their distribution in the public domain;
- 6)Browse adult sites.

Conclusion

In Conclusion, as we can see, the excessive use of social networks by young is showing serious damage to their mental health.On the Internet, teenagers have the opportunity to become asexual beings who kill everyone and everything, feel powerful and cool, that is, parents of the younger generation are set on social networks. It is a mistake by parents to give their children their mobile devices due to life problems,like working or doing household chores.Parents,pedagogues and psychologists should deal with the proper distribution of child's free time,without

the Internet, computer, and phone games in general, in the education of the young generation.

References

- 1) 2020 "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalari tahririyati;
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Main body

A social network is an online platform used for communication, dating, social relationships between people with similar interests or online connections, as well as for entertainment, music and movies and work purposes, and it has a lot of shows that have a negative impact on the level of youth in various forms. Currently, the most popular social networks around the world include sites, such as Telegram, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, WhatsApp, TikTok.

Snapchat, Reddit, Pinterest, LinkedIn [1]. All kinds of fictitious, fantastic and militant games, movies, video shows that are forbidden for minors to watch, and spreading secret information related to terrorism and extremism through religious sites of various forms, which are dangerous to human life, have a negative impact on the spirituality of the young generation.

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